

FELLOWSHIP

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Shillong

City Vision Document

A citizen-led vision narrative capturing stories,
concerns, and hopes for the city's future

About the Vision Document

This City Vision Document is a reflective learning assignment carried out as part of the Nāgrika Fellowship Programme. It is based on a limited number of conversations with citizens and observational research conducted over a few months by the fellow. The document does not claim to represent the complete or official vision of the city, but rather offers a citizen-led snapshot—built through individual stories, insights, and lived experiences gathered during the fellowship. The perspectives shared here reflect the voices of a few residents, selected to capture a range of age groups, professions, and neighborhoods. The document is not exhaustive and may not include all communities or viewpoints. This document is intended as a starting point for dialogue and reflection. We hope it encourages broader conversations about the city’s identity, challenges, and future possibilities.

The research and writing were undertaken independently by the fellow, within a framework of structured guidance provided by Nāgrika. This included thematic prompts, narrative-building exercises, regular mentorship and feedback sessions, all designed to support the fellow in shaping their city’s vision. The interpretations and final content remain those of the fellow.

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Nāgrika Fellowship

The **Nāgrika Fellowship Programme** has been designed to empower young individuals from diverse educational and geographic backgrounds, including students, gap-year participants, and early-career researchers, to positively engage with the history, socio-economic, governance, and cultural context of their cities. Focused on the youth of small and mid-sized cities, the fellowship is building local knowledge, enabling civic consciousness, and developing thought leaders who can address environmental, social, and infrastructural challenges. Over a period of six months, fellows gained tools for understanding and engaging with their cities.

A key component of the fellowship is the development of the **City Vision Document** by the fellows. This document is an emotionally grounded reflection of how citizens experience and imagine their city. Developed through conversations with diverse residents of the fellows' cities, it weaves together stories of everyday life, places of belonging, pressing concerns, and aspirations for the future. The document captures lived experiences and heartfelt insights to build a narrative that is authentic, accessible, and community-driven. It serves not only as a record of local voices but also as an invitation to reimagine the city through the eyes of those who call it home.

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Everyday Life

This theme explores the daily rhythms, routines, and interactions that shape how people experience their city. It highlights the ordinary yet meaningful details of our city's life and how citizens connect with their surroundings on a regular basis.

Voices of Concern

This theme brings out the issues and challenges that citizens face in their day-to-day lives such as poor infrastructure, lack of public transport, disappearing green spaces, water or waste management issues, safety concerns, or loss of cultural heritage.

Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging are spaces that hold emotional, cultural, or social significance for residents. This theme focuses on spaces that provide identity, memory, and a sense of home, the places where we feel connected, seen, and grounded.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow reflects citizens' aspirations for the city's future. This theme brings forward ideas, hopes, and solutions imagined by the people who live in and care for the city.

Why this Vision Document?

This City Vision Document has been put together to represent the thoughts, concerns, and experiences that residents hold about Shillong and how it is being shaped and managed today. Many of those who shared their views have spent most, if not all, of their lives in the city. They have seen it change over time, experienced its strengths and its gaps, and developed a clear understanding of what works and what does not.

This document starts from a simple idea: that the people who live in a city are best placed to speak about it. Their perspectives come from lived experience, not abstraction. In that sense, this is not just a collection of opinions, but a reflection of how the city is actually experienced on the ground. While the perspectives captured here are not exhaustive, they reflect recurring patterns and shared concerns across different parts of the city.

Meet Shillong

Shillong does not reveal itself all at once. It sits in the hills, wrapped in mist, its slopes carrying layers of memory that go beyond its familiar image as the “Scotland of the East.” The name itself is believed to be derived from Lei Shyllong, a revered deity in Khasi belief, believed to reside on the prominent Shillong Peak overlooking the city. When the British established it as the capital of undivided Assam, Shillong grew into an administrative and educational centre, drawing people, ideas, and influences into its fold. Over time, waves of migration, including a significant Bengali presence during the colonial and post-partition years, added to the city’s social fabric, shaping its institutions, neighbourhoods, and everyday interactions.

Today, Shillong carries all of this at once. It is a city of steep roads and shifting rhythms, where mornings begin early with school runs and long commutes, and where the day spills into markets, cafés, and roadside conversations. The landscape still holds its quiet beauty, but daily life unfolds in negotiation with congestion, distance, and change. Known for its close-knit communities and strong cultural identity, the city continues to balance what it has inherited with what it is becoming. In Shillong, the past is never too far away. It lingers in its institutions, its neighbourhoods, and in the ease with which strangers become familiar. Sit long enough with someone, and connections begin to surface—a shared locality, a mutual relative, a name that links you back to somewhere known. Belonging here is rarely distant; it is often just one conversation away!

Meet Citizens of Shillong

For a common citizen in the city, Shillong is not experienced as a single, uniform space. It reveals itself differently depending on who you are, what you do, and where you move within it. For vendors and shopkeepers across the city's markets, the day begins early. Dukan Doh (meat shops) and Dukan Sha & Ja (rice and tea stalls) are among the first to open, setting the pace for the day ahead. These spaces are not only centres of livelihood but also of regular interaction, where familiar faces return, and conversations unfold over time.

For school children and office-goers, the day is often defined by movement. Mornings are marked by urgency, as people navigate traffic that has become a constant part of the city's rhythm. Schedules are structured around congestion, and time is often measured by how long it takes to get from one place to another.

For taxi drivers, each day carries a degree of uncertainty. Earnings are not fixed and depend on demand, timing, and chance. Some days are steady, while others fall short, making the city feel unpredictable in how it sustains those who depend on it.

For many young people and those still searching for opportunities, the city can feel both familiar and limiting. While it offers a strong sense of belonging, it does not always provide the pathways needed to move forward. This often

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creates a quiet tension, where people remain connected to Shillong, even as they consider leaving it in search of something more stable.

At the same time, there are those who have witnessed the city change over generations. As one elderly resident recalled, “When we were kids, horse carts were used as the main mode of transportation.” Such memories reflect not just a shift in infrastructure, but in the pace and character of the city itself. Across these experiences, Shillong does not exist as a single narrative, but as a collection of lived realities. What connects them is a shared adaptation to change, and an ongoing effort to find stability within it.

Shillong: Facts in Brief

State	Meghalaya
District	East Khasi Hills
Population	5,32,490 (Estimated)
Area	290.51 square kilometres
Type of city government	Municipal Board
Languages	Khasi, Garo, Pnar, English, Hindi, etc.

Character of the City

Shillong is often described as a place that experiences four seasons in a single day. Mornings can begin with a lingering chill, afternoons open up to brief sunlight, and by evening, mist and rain quietly return. This shifting weather is not an exception but a pattern, shaping how people dress, move, and plan their day. Set across a hilly terrain, the city rises and falls with steep roads, narrow lanes, and winding paths that make movement feel less about distance and more about effort. The landscape is not something you pass through; it is something you constantly adjust to.

Fig. 1: An overview of the junction at Khyndailad (Police Bazaar)

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Life in Shillong unfolds through a mix of formal and informal rhythms. Markets, small businesses, street vendors, and local enterprises form a large part of the city's everyday economy, while education and government services draw people in from across the state. Culture is not confined to designated spaces. It extends into the public realm through music, street performances, and spontaneous gatherings that briefly turn busy areas into shared cultural spaces. Conversations at tea stalls and the ease of everyday interactions blur the line between social and economic life, shaping a way of living that feels both active and rooted.

Personal Connection to the City:

My connection with Shillong began in my early school years, when my understanding of the city was confined to the short stretch between home and school in Barik. For a long time, even into my secondary school years, Shillong existed within this limited geography, familiar yet only partially known. It was only gradually that I began to move beyond these boundaries, exploring different parts of the city and forming a broader sense of what it meant to belong to it.

In more recent years, as a young adult, this relationship has taken on a different texture. The pace of life here feels noticeably slower, something that can be both limiting and grounding at the same time. Days do not rush in the way they might in larger cities, and while this can at times feel restrictive, it also allows for a certain stillness that is increasingly rare. At the same time, Shillong has come to be associated, especially by those from outside, with its growing concert and music culture. Friends often speak of the city through this lens, drawn to its reputation for live performances and events. While it is

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difficult to place this within a fixed sense of whether it defines the city or not, it remains one of the more visible ways in which Shillong is experienced and understood today.

Looking back, while the city has undoubtedly undergone change, it does not feel entirely disconnected from what it once was. Instead, it carries forward traces of its past within its present, allowing continuity and change to coexist in ways that are both visible and subtle.

Fig. 2: Bus Stand located in Barik Point, Shillong

Listening to the City

Across conversations, a clear tension emerges between what development currently looks like and what people actually need. Many residents feel that the city is becoming increasingly vehicle-oriented, with road expansion prioritised over pedestrian safety, accessibility, and everyday usability. Footpaths remain broken, blocked, or absent, making movement difficult, especially for vulnerable groups such as persons with disabilities. At the same time, traffic congestion, poor drainage, and unplanned growth continue to shape daily life, creating a sense that the city is struggling to keep up with itself. While large projects and commercial spaces are expanding, they often fail to address these more immediate, lived concerns.

Equally striking is the lack of inclusive and accessible public spaces. Across age groups and professions, people expressed the need for more green, open, and non-commercial areas where they can simply exist without the pressure to spend. Natural spaces remain deeply valued as sites of rest and reflection, yet they are increasingly under threat. The absence of such “third spaces” not only limits recreation but also affects social life, mental well-being, and the ability of communities to gather. Informal spaces such as street markets and vendor areas, while often contested, continue to play a crucial role in affordability, safety, and the everyday vibrancy of the city.

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Finally, there is a shared sense that governance and participation remain limited. While citizens are aware of the issues shaping their city, many feel there are few accessible or transparent channels to voice concerns or influence decisions. Fear, political structures, and lack of trust often discourage open engagement. At the same time, there is a strong desire for more accountability, better implementation of policies, and greater inclusion in planning processes. Across these narratives, one idea remains consistent: for Shillong to move forward, development must shift from being infrastructure-driven to people-centred, grounded in everyday realities, and shaped through collective participation.

Glossary and Local Terms

Word or Phrase	Translation / Meaning
<i>Lei Shyllong</i>	A revered Khasi deity believed to reside at Shillong Peak overlooking the city. The name “Shillong” is widely understood to be derived from this deity, reflecting the peak’s sacred significance in Khasi cosmology and local folklore.
<i>Jadoh</i>	A traditional Khasi rice dish, typically cooked with pork and flavoured with spices, often prepared using pork blood which gives it its distinctive colour and taste
<i>Seng Samla</i>	Community-based youth groups present at the shnong (locality) or church level, where young people engage in social, cultural, and collective activities
<i>Dorbar Shnong</i>	The village council that functions as a local self-governance and administrative body among the Khasi people, responsible for managing community affairs at the shnong (locality) level
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Everyday Life

Everyday Life

Morning in Shillong begins earlier than it should. School children leave home well ahead of time, their routines shaped not by distance but by the uncertainty of traffic. Roads leading towards Laitumkrah, with its cluster of educational institutions, and towards the office areas of Secretariat Hills and Lachumiere slowly fill, as students and office-goers make their way through a city where even short commutes demand planning. In different parts of the city, rows of two-wheeler taxi riders wait by the roadside, watching for passengers, ready to navigate routes that larger vehicles struggle to move through. What should be a simple journey becomes a daily negotiation, where time stretches, and movement feels heavier than it ought to.

Fig. 3: An interaction between two women at Iewduh market

As the day unfolds, the city gathers in its shared spaces. In Iewduh, the city's oldest market, people from nearby villages and districts arrive, carrying goods, exchanging stories, and sustaining rhythms that have long defined the city's everyday life. Elsewhere, movement continues between markets, workplaces, and small informal stops that double as places of pause. By evening, the city swells once more as people begin their return, waiting for transport, adjusting routes, and navigating the same constraints in reverse. And then, almost as suddenly, it recedes. Streets thin out, shutters close, and life retreats indoors, leaving behind a city that feels both active and contained, where the effort of the day quietly settles into the night.

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Daily life in Shillong is shaped by movement that rarely follows logic. A commute of a few kilometres can stretch into an hour, turning time into something uncertain and unreliable. Students leave home long before necessary, and workdays quietly extend to avoid peak congestion. As an **Urban Planner** working in the city shared, *“What should ideally take 20–30 minutes often extends to more than an hour.”* Public transport exists, but not in ways people can depend on, as it is limited to high traffic areas, pushing many towards privately owned cars or two-wheeler taxis.

For many residents, especially those in informal work, everyday life is less about convenience and more about survival. Street vending, small-scale production, and daily wage labour sustain households, often without consistent institutional support. As **Shane Thabah (General Secretary of Meghalaya & Greater Shillong Progressive Hawkers and Street Vendors Association)** puts it, *“The system does not really work for the poor.”* Rising costs of living, limited protection, and uneven access to opportunities make the city difficult to adapt to economically, even as it continues to attract people seeking better prospects.

Across experiences, a common thread emerges: the need to constantly adapt. Broken roads, poor drainage, inconsistent services, and unmanaged growth are no longer disruptions; they are everyday routines. As **Nicholas Kharkamni (Eco-activist)** observed, *“We don’t live with systems working smoothly; we live by figuring things out as we go.”* Over time, this creates a quiet fatigue, where expectations are lowered, and coping replaces demand. In such a context, expressions of dissent, including hunger strikes, begin to appear not as extreme measures, but as some of the few viable ways through which demands are addressed.

Older residents often recall a different Shillong—one that felt slower, more walkable, and more closely knit. Visiting relatives, walking through neighbourhoods, and spending time outdoors were once ordinary parts of daily life. As **one Senior Citizen** reflected, such routines have faded over time, as congestion and time constraints reshape everyday life. Today, these experiences feel harder to sustain, requiring more effort, more patience, and more adjustment.

Residents with mobility challenges often experience the city very differently, where everyday movement requires constant caution. Spaces that may seem accessible to others become difficult to navigate due to uneven surfaces and poor infrastructure. As **one resident with a locomotor disability** shared, *“I pray before stepping out that I do not fall again. Slippery roads and broken footpaths make everyday movement a struggle, and what was once a very active life is now mostly limited to home and college.”* His experience reflects how access to the city is uneven, shaped not only by social and economic factors but by how infrastructure enables or restricts movement in everyday life.

Structural Analysis

The everyday experiences described by residents are not isolated inconveniences but outcomes of deeper structural gaps in how Shillong has grown and is governed. At its core, the city reflects the challenges of an unplanned urban transition. What was once a small hill town has expanded rapidly without corresponding investments in infrastructure, public transport, and spatial planning. As a result, systems that should support daily life, roads, drainage, and pedestrian infrastructure are constantly under strain. Traffic congestion, for instance, is not simply a function of more vehicles, but of limited road capacity, lack of alternative transport systems, and weak enforcement of traffic discipline.

A key structural issue lies in the concentration of opportunities within the city. Shillong continues to function as the primary centre for education, healthcare, and employment in the state. This draws people from across districts, intensifying pressure on already limited infrastructure. As highlighted in multiple accounts, movement within the city becomes a daily negotiation because the system is designed around centralisation rather than distributed growth. The absence of strong secondary urban centres across Meghalaya means that Shillong absorbs both opportunity and stress, creating a cycle that is difficult to break.

Mobility challenges are further compounded by the decline and inadequacy of public transport systems. Another structural concern is the lack of accessible and well-maintained public spaces. As several respondents pointed out, Shillong has very few “third spaces” where people can gather without the expectation of spending money. Parks are limited, often regulated by timings, and do not integrate seamlessly into everyday life. In the absence of such spaces, informal alternatives – tea stalls, markets, cafés – take on this role. While these spaces are socially vibrant, their existence also reflects a gap in formal urban design that prioritises commercial development over inclusive public environments.

Governance and institutional gaps also play a significant role in shaping everyday life. The absence of an elected municipal body, coupled with overlapping jurisdictions under the Sixth Schedule, has created ambiguities in urban management. Decision-making is often fragmented, and long-term planning becomes difficult to implement. At the same time, limited transparency and weak mechanisms for citizen participation contribute to a sense of disconnection between residents and institutions. As a result, while people experience problems daily, there are few accessible channels through which they can influence systemic change.

Finally, there is an interplay between infrastructure and civic behaviour that shapes how the city functions. Issues such as waste management, encroachment, and traffic discipline cannot be attributed solely to either the state or citizens. Instead, they reflect a feedback loop where inadequate systems discourage responsible behaviour, and a lack of civic responsibility further weakens already strained systems. This is evident in the deterioration of shared spaces and the normalisation of conditions that residents themselves recognise as unacceptable.

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At the same time, the city continues to function through a range of informal systems and social practices that compensate for these structural gaps. Shared taxis and two-wheelers, despite contributing to congestion, remain essential to everyday mobility by providing flexibility and connectivity that formal public transport does not. Similarly, informal economic spaces such as street markets and *Jadoh* stalls serve dual roles, supporting livelihoods while also acting as accessible, everyday spaces of interaction in the absence of adequate public infrastructure.

Equally important are the social networks that underpin daily life in the city. Acts of mutual support, whether among neighbours, commuters, or informal workers, often bridge the gap between what the system fails to provide and what people need to get through the day. In this way, Shillong's functionality rests not only on formal governance structures but also on the adaptability and interdependence of its residents.

Reflection

What these everyday experiences reveal is that Shillong is not struggling because of a lack of potential, but because of a mismatch between how the city functions and how it is being planned and governed. The city continues to grow, but without systems that prioritise people's everyday realities. Instead of enabling ease, existing structures often make daily life more difficult, forcing residents to constantly adapt and compensate.

If policymakers understood this, they would realise that development cannot be reduced to infrastructure expansion alone. There is a need to make better and more appropriate use of existing infrastructure, while ensuring that future planning is thoughtful and forward-looking, with a vision that extends far beyond immediate needs. Development must be rooted in everyday experiences and aligned with what citizens actually need, whether it is walkability, accessible public spaces, or reliable transport, rather than being driven primarily by isolated projects.

More importantly, they would recognise that citizens are not disengaged, but constrained by limited avenues for participation. Creating transparent and accessible platforms for public input could bridge this gap, allowing governance to become more responsive and grounded. Without this shift, the city risks continuing on a path where problems are managed in isolation, rather than addressed at their source.

Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging

Iewduh and Everyday Markets

Markets such as Iewduh and other smaller markets function as some of the most enduring shared spaces in the city. They are used by a wide cross-section of people, from local residents to those travelling in from nearby districts, not only for trade but for interaction and exchange. Tea stalls, street vendors, and small shops extend this experience beyond transactions, creating informal spaces where conversations unfold naturally. These markets have long been central to Shillong's everyday life, acting as both economic and social anchors. However, increasing congestion, regulatory pressures, and changing commercial patterns are slowly reshaping their character. While they remain inclusive spaces, their future depends on balancing livelihood needs with urban management.

Ward's Lake and Phan Nonglait Park

Spaces like Ward's Lake and Phan Nonglait Park have long existed as some of the few formal public spaces in Shillong. For many, especially during their school years, these places were part of everyday routines, whether for walks, brief outings, or simply spending time outdoors. They continue to hold emotional and nostalgic value, even if visits have become less frequent.

However, rather than evolving with the city, these spaces now feel increasingly limited. They remain among the only recognisable public spaces available, but their design, regulation, and scale have not kept pace with the growing needs of the population. As a result, they are visited occasionally rather than being part of everyday life.

In recent years, Ward's Lake has also been used to host events from time to time. While these bring activity into the space, they can disrupt the calm and open nature that people associate with it. This reflects a broader challenge in how such spaces are managed, where different uses do not always align with their original purpose.

Neighbourhoods, Homes, and Kinship Spaces

In Shillong, belonging is often rooted less in formal public spaces and more within homes and neighbourhoods. The importance of the matriarch in Khasi society makes spaces like a grandmother's home central to identity and continuity. Everyday interactions with neighbours, whether through conversation or shared routines, create a sense of familiarity and connection. These spaces have existed across generations, forming the social backbone of the city. However, changing lifestyles, increasing individualism, and digital forms of interaction are gradually weakening these bonds. While still deeply meaningful, such spaces are becoming less visible in the larger narrative of the city.

PLACES OF BELONGING

Cafés, Food Stalls, and Informal Third Spaces

In the absence of accessible public spaces, cafés, street food stalls, and small gathering spots have become important sites of belonging, especially for young people. These spaces are used for socialising, studying, and informal meetings, often on a daily basis. As one student shared, *“the only places we hang out are cafés, food stalls, or our college campus... parks are enclosed, fenced, and often require entry fees.”* Their rise reflects both demand and adaptation, as people create their own ‘third spaces’ within a limited urban environment. However, these are largely monetised spaces, which makes access uneven. Their growing importance also points to a structural gap, where the city has not been able to provide enough inclusive, non-commercial environments for people to gather freely.

Churches and Community Organisations

Churches continue to function as strong spaces of belonging across Shillong, particularly through youth groups such as Seng Samla, both in church and at the locality level. These spaces bring people together through shared activities, leadership, and community engagement. They have historically played a significant role in shaping social life and continue to do so in many localities. However, their presence is uneven, with declining participation in some areas. As one school teacher shared, *“While Seng Samla remains active in some localities, its presence has declined in others. In my own locality, community youth organisations are not as visible as they once were.”* While they remain important, their ability to serve as universal spaces of belonging is influenced by changing social dynamics and varying levels of community engagement.

Fig. 5: Interior of the chapel at Don Bosco Youth Centre, Laitumkhrah.

PLACES OF BELONGING

Streets as Spaces of Work and Belonging

For many, especially those in the informal sector, the streets themselves are places of belonging. Street hawkers, vendors, and small businesses use these spaces not only for livelihood but also for building networks of support and solidarity. These streets enable interaction across communities and contribute to the everyday vibrancy of the city, from the sale of handicrafts and seasonal fruits to local food that draws both residents and visitors. As one hawker notes, “I can proudly say that it is we hawkers that bring tourists to Kyndailad.” They have evolved over time as organic spaces of economic and social exchange. At the same time, they are marked by fragility, shaped by evictions, lack of formal recognition, and tensions over space. While they remain inclusive in practice, their legitimacy within the city’s planning framework is often uncertain.

What is affecting these places?

The places that shape belonging in Shillong are not disappearing entirely, but they are changing in ways that affect how people experience them. In markets such as Lewduh, the issue is less about overdevelopment and more about neglect. Despite remaining central to everyday life, parts of the market exist in a dilapidated condition, with limited maintenance or repair. Over time, this affects not just physical infrastructure but also the dignity and comfort of those who depend on it daily.

In contrast, spaces like Ward's Lake are being reshaped through new forms of use. The growing trend of hosting festivals and music events has added to their visibility and relevance, reinforcing their role as places where people gather. At the same time, this shift raises questions about their original purpose as calm, accessible public spaces. What strengthens their identity in one sense may also dilute it in another.

Neighbourhoods and kinship-based spaces are undergoing quieter but equally significant changes. The shift towards more nuclear and independent family structures has reduced the everyday interactions that once defined these environments. The role of the matriarch, especially figures like grandmothers who anchored family life and continuity, is becoming less central in many households. As these structures evolve, the informal networks of care and belonging they sustained are also weakening.

Similarly, community-based institutions such as Seng Samla, operating under the Dorbar Shnong or church networks, are seeing a decline in participation in certain localities. These organisations once created regular opportunities for collective engagement, particularly among youth. Their gradual weakening reflects broader shifts in how people engage with community life, where time constraints, changing priorities, and alternative forms of social interaction are reshaping participation.

PLACES OF BELONGING

Across these spaces, the fragility lies not in sudden loss, but in gradual transformation. Whether through neglect, repurposing, or changing social structures, the everyday foundations of belonging in Shillong are being redefined in ways that are subtle, uneven, and often difficult to reverse.

Reflection

Across these spaces, a sense of belonging is not evenly experienced. Markets, streets, and informal gathering spots tend to remain the most inclusive, where people from different backgrounds interact with relative ease. They are accessible, familiar, and woven into everyday routines. At the same time, access to more formal or comfortable spaces is often shaped by the ability to spend, by time restrictions, or by confidence in navigating those environments. For many, especially those with fewer resources or limited mobility, the city offers fewer spaces where they can simply exist without negotiation. Belonging, in this sense, is not just about place, but about who feels at ease within it.

There are also quieter exclusions. Community structures such as Seng Samla continue to create spaces for engagement, particularly for youth, but they do not include everyone. Those who are not interested in such groups, or who are less connected to religious or community-based institutions, may find fewer avenues for participation. At the same time, as neighbourhood ties weaken, opportunities for informal, everyday interaction are also reducing. Younger people may find belonging in cafés or event-based spaces, while others feel increasingly disconnected from both traditional and emerging forms of social life. In this shift, belonging becomes more fragmented, experienced differently across age, interest, and circumstance.

Development in these spaces, therefore, requires careful thought, not only in terms of physical change but in understanding what these places carry. Markets like lewduh are not just economic centres but social ecosystems. Spaces like Ward's Lake hold layers of memory that go beyond their present use. Neighbourhoods and informal gathering spots sustain relationships that are not easily rebuilt once lost.

To intervene in these spaces without recognising their social and cultural weight risks reducing them to mere infrastructure or commercial zones. Development here should be careful because these places carry memory, routine, and forms of belonging that cannot be easily replaced once disrupted.

Voices of Concern

Voices of Concern

Transport and Mobility Breakdown

Every day movement in Shillong has become unpredictable, time-consuming, and mentally exhausting. Despite short distances, commuting often takes over an hour due to congestion, poor road infrastructure, and the absence of a reliable public transport system. The decline of government bus services and overdependence on private operators have made mobility both inefficient and expensive. For many, planning their day revolves around avoiding traffic rather than actual priorities.

Fig. 6: Locally operated buses (Bos Smit) serving as a primary mode of public transport.

“The city is being designed for car owners, not for pedestrians. Walkability is completely ignored. You cannot keep accommodating more vehicles in a small hill city and expect things to improve.” – Mr B. Dutta, Retd. Director of Urban Affairs

Who raised it: Students, working professionals, SHG members, urban planners

Why it keeps repeating: Weak public investment, fragmented transport governance, and rising private vehicle ownership

This concern persists because... mobility is treated as an individual responsibility rather than a public system to be planned and sustained

VOICES OF CONCERN

Poor Urban Planning and Infrastructure Strain

Shillong's growth has not been matched by planning. Narrow roads, broken footpaths, poor drainage, and constant construction reflect a city expanding without long-term vision. At the same time, existing infrastructure remains underutilised. Facilities such as the ISBT in Mawiong remain inoperational, while recently developed spaces like the shopping complex in Polo, despite being formally inaugurated, have yet to become fully functional.

“Footpaths, manholes, potholes, and uneven roads pose daily risks... Ambitious projects are often taken up without feasibility, leading to repeated reconstruction.” – Urban Planner

Who raised it: Urban planners, school teachers, and general residents

Why it keeps repeating: Lack of coordinated and long-term planning, short-term project cycles, and weak enforcement of regulations

This concern persists because... infrastructure development is reactive and fragmented rather than guided by long-term planning.

Governance Gaps and Lack of Accountability

A major issue lies not just in systems failing, but in the absence of clear responsibility. Overlapping jurisdictions, absence of an elected municipal body, and institutional ambiguity create a situation where problems persist without resolution. Citizens often do not know who to hold accountable.

“People talk, protest, file RTIs—but very little changes. The problem is not lack of information, it is lack of consequences.” – Nicholas Kharkamni

Who raised it: Activists, retired officials, active citizens

Why it keeps repeating: Institutional fragmentation, unclear authority, and weak accountability mechanisms

This concern persists because... governance structures exist in form but fail in function.

Rising Cost of Living and Economic Inequality

Shillong is becoming increasingly expensive, particularly for those in the informal sector. Daily wage earners, domestic workers, and small vendors struggle to meet basic needs, while opportunities for upward mobility remain limited. Economic gaps are becoming more visible across the city.

Fig. 7: Local vendors selling fresh produce and handcrafted goods, reflecting everyday livelihoods and small-scale enterprise

“Even petty jobs don’t pay enough to feed a family... there are no real protections for people trying to survive.” – Mayfereen Ryntathiang

Who raised it: SHG members, informal workers, social observers

Why it keeps repeating: Limited livelihood diversification, weak labour protections, and dependence on low-paying informal work

This concern persists because... economic growth has not translated into equitable opportunities for all sections of society.

Pressure from Centralisation and Migration

Shillong continues to function as the primary hub for education, healthcare, and employment, drawing people from across Meghalaya and other Northeastern states. This concentration intensifies pressure on housing, infrastructure, and public services, while also reshaping the social and cultural fabric of the city.

“Shillong attracts students from everywhere, but there aren’t enough hostels... in many areas now, I feel like a tourist in my own city.” – Shawn Marbaniang, College Student.

VOICES OF CONCERN

Who raised it: Students, planners, residents

Why it keeps repeating: Lack of development in secondary towns and continued centralisation of opportunities

This concern persists because... regional imbalances push people into the city without expanding its capacity to absorb them.

Environmental Degradation and Civic Behaviour

Shillong's natural environment, once central to its identity, is under increasing stress. Waste mismanagement, pollution of water bodies, and loss of green cover are compounded by both weak systems and poor civic practices. Environmental decline is now embedded in everyday life. Although laws and regulations exist, their enforcement is not visibly effective, resulting in both institutions and citizens contributing to the problem.

“Wah Umkhrah has turned from a stream into a drain... people litter without thinking, and unless rules hit their pockets, nothing will change.” – Nelson Lyngdoh, Content Creator

Who raised it: Citizens, environmental observers, planners

Why it keeps repeating: Lack of strict enforcement, weak waste systems, and low civic accountability

This concern persists because... environmental responsibility is diffused between the state and citizens, with neither fully addressing it.

Exclusion and Inaccessibility in Everyday Spaces

The city remains difficult to navigate for many, especially persons with disabilities. Broken footpaths, encroachments, poor lighting, and unsafe roads make basic movement challenging. Accessibility is rarely integrated into planning, limiting participation in everyday life.

“Footpaths are broken or blocked, and there are hardly any accessible spaces... for someone like me, even stepping out requires constant caution.” – Person with Locomotor Disability.

Who raised it: Persons with disabilities, elderly residents, and general citizens.

VOICES OF CONCERN

Why it keeps repeating: Lack of inclusive planning and absence of accessibility standards in infrastructure

This concern persists because... disability is treated as a welfare issue, not a fundamental aspect of urban design.

Emerging patterns across interviews

Across the interviews, certain patterns consistently emerge, revealing how different groups experience the city in distinct yet overlapping ways.

Youth concerns are centred around mobility, identity, and opportunity. Students and young professionals repeatedly describe long, unpredictable commutes, lack of affordable housing, and limited public infrastructure that support their daily routines. At the same time, there is a quieter anxiety around cultural belonging, where parts of the city feel increasingly unfamiliar, shaped by changing demographics and market preferences.

Women, informal workers, and marginalised groups reflect the intersection of economic pressure, mobility challenges, and limited institutional support. SHG members and workers in informal sectors describe rising costs of living, dependence on unreliable transport, and the strain of sustaining livelihoods with low and inconsistent incomes. Street vendors speak of ongoing struggles for recognition, space, and fair implementation of policies meant to protect them. For persons with disabilities, the city presents everyday physical barriers that restrict independent movement, reinforcing exclusion from public life.

At a broader level, **civic complaints** converge around governance gaps and poor planning. Residents consistently point to unclear accountability, fragmented institutions, and infrastructure that fails to meet growing demands. Traffic congestion, inadequate public transport, and the deterioration of basic systems such as drainage and pedestrian infrastructure are experienced as daily constraints rather than occasional disruptions.

These lived experiences closely align with **local media narratives**, which frequently report on traffic congestion, delays in infrastructure projects, and environmental concerns such as illegal dumping of waste and pollution of water bodies. Issues like illegal coal mining and gaps in public service delivery also feature prominently in public discourse, reinforcing the concerns raised by citizens. However, as several respondents noted, awareness does not always translate into action, contributing to a sense that problems persist despite being widely recognised.

VOICES OF CONCERN

Environmental concerns emerge as a deeply felt and visible layer of everyday life in Shillong. Residents repeatedly point to the degradation of natural systems that once defined the city, particularly the pollution of water bodies, unchecked waste disposal, and the gradual loss of green cover due to unregulated construction. Streams such as Wah Umkhrah are frequently cited as examples of this decline, reflecting how ecological damage has become normalised in daily experience. At the same time, these issues are not attributed solely to governance failures. Citizens acknowledge the role of everyday behaviour, especially littering and poor waste practices, creating a shared but unresolved responsibility.

Reflection:

The concerns raised across interviews reveal a city where everyday difficulties are closely tied to deeper structural issues, but they also point to quieter concerns that are often normalised over time. While traffic, infrastructure, and governance dominate visible discussions, there are underlying shifts that shape how people relate to the city and its systems.

A key concern that emerges beneath the surface is the **erosion of trust in institutions**—both formal and traditional. Respondents reflect a growing scepticism towards governance systems, where accountability feels distant and outcomes are uncertain. This is accompanied by a gradual normalisation of inefficiency, where people adjust their routines around dysfunction rather than expecting systems to improve.

In distinguishing between what is **systemic** and what is **incidental**, it becomes clear that many visible problems—traffic congestion, improper waste management, or delays in service delivery—are symptoms of deeper structural gaps in planning, governance, and regional development. These systemic issues shape everyday life in consistent and far-reaching ways. In contrast, incidental issues such as temporary disruptions or localised inefficiencies are often outcomes of these larger gaps rather than independent problems. For instance, the centralisation of educational institutions, office establishments and markets in a particular area or in Shillong as a whole causes incidental occurrences such as traffic jams.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow

A City that Retains its Identity

There is a strong and recurring concern that as Shillong develops, it risks losing the very character that makes it distinct. Residents speak about identity not just in cultural terms, but in how the city feels—its pace, its familiarity, and its rootedness in history. The fear is not of change itself, but of a kind of development that erases rather than adapts.

Fig. 8: Public bus featuring graffiti of monoliths and a girl in traditional attire

“I do not want my city to lose its originality and authenticity, the history that it has.”
– Megan Syiem

Why do people believe it is possible: Shillong still holds visible traces of its past in its neighbourhoods, social life, and everyday interactions, which residents continue to value and recognise.

This hope can remain alive if... development builds on existing cultural and historical contexts instead of replacing them.

Functional and Accountable Governance

Many respondents do not imagine an idealised future, but a city that simply functions with clarity and accountability. The aspiration is for systems that are predictable, responsive, and transparent, where roles are clearly defined, and decisions translate into outcomes.

DREAMS FOR TOMORROW

“When I think about the future of Shillong, I do not imagine something dramatic or utopian. What I hope for is something much more basic – a city that functions with discipline, clarity, and accountability.” – Nicholas Kharkamni

Why do people believe it is possible: Institutional frameworks and legal mechanisms already exist, and there are examples where sustained pressure has led to action.

This hope can remain alive if... governance structures are strengthened, roles clarified, and accountability consistently enforced.

Development that Prioritises Everyday Needs

Residents express a clear distinction between visible development and meaningful development. While commercial projects and enclosed spaces are increasing, they often do not address everyday challenges. There is a strong call for infrastructure that directly improves the daily life of the citizens.

“The mindset of people is also changing, and more residents are beginning to understand how cities function and how they should be governed. One day, I believe we will have a proper city government. When people become part of the decision-making process, services will also improve.” – Shillong Municipal Board Official.

“Development cannot simply mean building roads or large infrastructure. It must address the everyday realities of people’s lives – livelihoods, social protection, public transport, and accessible services.” – Angela Rangad, Prominent Activist.

Why do people believe it is possible: Shillong already has the basic structure of a functioning city; the gap lies in prioritisation rather than absence.

This hope can remain alive if... planning shifts towards practical, everyday infrastructure over symbolic or high-visibility projects.

Inclusive and Accessible Public Spaces

There is a growing demand for public spaces that are open, inclusive, and not tied to consumption. Residents emphasise the need for parks, walking areas, and shared spaces that support everyday interaction across age groups and social backgrounds.

“I want parks that are safe, accessible, and free spaces where children, elders, and even pets can coexist without the pressure to spend money.” – Urban Planner

DREAMS FOR TOMORROW

Why do people believe it is possible: Shillong's natural landscape and existing social culture provide a strong foundation for developing such spaces.

This hope can remain alive if... public spaces are treated as essential urban infrastructure and designed for universal access.

Environmental Protection as a Core Priority

The protection of Shillong's natural environment is seen not as an optional goal but as central to its future. Residents express concern over the loss of green cover, water sources, and ecological balance, and emphasise the need for sustainability to guide development.

"If there is one thing I don't want to change... it is the natural beauty of Shillong. Everything else can change, but nature must be protected." – Youth Respondent

Why do people believe it is possible: There is a deep cultural and emotional connection to nature, supported by traditional practices that value conservation.

This hope can remain alive if... environmental considerations are integrated into all levels of planning and enforced consistently.

A More Liveable and Walkable City

Many respondents imagine a Shillong where movement is easier, safer, and more human-centred. This includes better footpaths, reduced congestion, and infrastructure that prioritises pedestrians over vehicles.

"Life in Shillong would be slightly better with better footpaths, traffic discipline, and proper maintenance... even small changes could make a big difference." – Police Bazaar resident

Why do people believe it is possible: Shillong's scale and geography make it well-suited for walkability if supported by the right infrastructure.

This hope can remain alive if... mobility planning shifts towards pedestrian-friendly and people-centric design.

A Balanced and Decentralised City

There is a clear recognition that Shillong cannot continue to absorb all economic, educational, and social pressures. Residents envision a future where development is more evenly distributed, reducing the burden on the city.

DREAMS FOR TOMORROW

“I hope the city moves away from over-centralisation and instead adopts decentralised, cluster-based systems for services and infrastructure.” – Urban Planner

Why do people believe it is possible: There is increasing awareness of the limits of centralisation and the need for alternative development models.

This hope can remain alive if... planning expands beyond Shillong and invests in secondary centres and regional growth.

Condition for Hope

The aspirations expressed by residents ultimately point to a shared need for a city that functions with clarity, balance, and responsiveness. Across concerns around identity, infrastructure, environment, and governance, what emerges is not a demand for rapid and drastic transformation, but for a more grounded and coherent approach to urban development. At its core, these hopes reflect a desire for Shillong to remain liveable and rooted, while becoming more efficient and equitable in how it is planned and managed.

To move in this direction, both systems and behaviours must shift. In the short term, there are practical improvements that can significantly enhance everyday life, such as better traffic management, continuous footpaths, maintenance of existing infrastructure, and more accessible public spaces. These are achievable within current capacities, provided there is administrative focus and enforcement. At the same time, deeper structural issues such as fragmented governance, over-centralisation, and the absence of coordinated urban planning require long-term reform. Without addressing these, many smaller interventions risk remaining temporary or uneven in impact in the long run.

Responsibility for change, however, is not evenly distributed. While citizens play a role in maintaining discipline and participating in civic processes, the primary responsibility lies with institutions to deliver functional systems, ensure accountability, and create avenues for meaningful engagement. At the same time, several respondents point to a gradual decline in the sense of collectivism that once shaped community life. Where neighbourhoods and shared spaces earlier enabled interaction and mutual responsibility, there is now a visible shift towards more private and individualised ways of living. This shift is also reflected in everyday civic behaviour, where awareness does not always translate into practice. As Ibankyntiew Mawrie, Journalist and Co-founder of 4FrontMedia, notes, *“Civic responsibility cannot be enforced only through government policies or fines. It has to come from individuals themselves. Issues like littering and waste disposal continue despite awareness and monitoring.”*

Fig. 9: Bamboo crafts (Khoh and Polo) highlighting local craftsmanship and livelihoods.

What is in the way of us realising our City's dreams?

What stands in the way is not a lack of ideas, but a growing disconnect between systems, people, and the values that once held the city together. Governance remains fragmented, with unclear responsibilities and weak enforcement, which makes even well-intentioned plans feel distant from everyday life. As Mr B. Dutta (Retd Director of Urban Affairs) stated, *“There is constant confusion about jurisdiction, who controls what, who is responsible for which area. We are fighting amongst ourselves instead of addressing the city’s problems.”*

At the same time, the way land is being used reflects a deeper shift. In a place where land has long carried collective and cultural meaning, its increasing commodification signals a move away from shared responsibility. This is not only a planning issue, but also a social one.

The principle of *Tip Briew Tip Blei*, to know and respect one another, once shaped how people related to both community and place. Today, that sense of mutual accountability feels less visible, as life becomes more private and individualised, and public concerns are no longer collectively held in the same way.

DREAMS FOR TOMORROW

There is also a gap between willingness and access. People want to engage, but meaningful and transparent avenues for participation remain limited, leaving many voices unheard in decisions that shape the city. As Angela Rangad, activist, points out, *“Citizens should not be kept in the dark about decisions that shape their city. Information should be proactively shared with the public, rather than being disclosed only after someone files a request.”*

Ultimately, the challenge lies in alignment. Until governance becomes clearer, land use becomes more responsible, and a sense of collective responsibility is revived, the city’s dreams risk remaining part of conversation rather than becoming part of everyday life.

Fig. 10: View of Umiam Lake from Umbir.

Fig. 11: A thrift store located at Laitumkhrah, Shillong.

Fig. 12: Kwai (betel nut), which symbolises hospitality and social connection.

Policy Insights

Policy Insights

Mobility and Public Transport Gaps

Issue

Mobility in Shillong is shaped by the absence of a reliable and accessible public transport system. For most residents, daily movement depends on shared taxis, which operate without standardised fares or routes. While they remain flexible and widely used, this informality creates uncertainty and limits affordability for regular commuters.

At the same time, rising vehicle numbers and narrow road networks have intensified congestion, making travel time unpredictable and often inefficient. Interventions such as multi-level parking projects in parts of the city indicate a focus on managing vehicles rather than improving mobility itself. This raises questions about whether current approaches are addressing the root issue or simply accommodating its symptoms.

Short-Term Improvements

- Introduce fare standardisation for shared taxis based on distance or route.
- Strengthen traffic management and enforcement to improve flow on existing roads.
- Improve and encourage pedestrian movement through safer and continuous footpaths, especially in high-density areas.
- Introduce measures to discourage excessive private vehicle use, such as stricter parking regulations in core areas.

Medium-Term Improvements

- Ensure effective operation and maintenance of the recently introduced bus service (*Bos Jong Phi*) under the Urban Affairs Department.
- Draw lessons from previous public transport attempts to improve reliability, frequency, and public trust.
- Develop basic route integration between buses and shared taxis to improve coverage and last-mile connectivity.

Long-Term Structural Changes

- Shift investment priorities from vehicle-centric infrastructure towards a reliable and accessible public transport system.
- Develop a comprehensive mobility plan that prioritises public and non-motorised transport over private vehicles.

Key Stakeholders: Transport Department, Urban Affairs Department, Shillong Municipal Board, Traffic Police, Taxi Associations, Citizens

POLICY INSIGHTS

Shrinking and Unequal Access to Public Spaces

Issue

Across the city, there is a visible decline in accessible, open public spaces. While commercial complexes and enclosed developments are increasing, they often replace or limit spaces that were once freely used by residents. Parks are fenced, entry is restricted or monetised, and everyday access to greenery within the city is uneven. As a result, many people, especially young people, are pushed towards cafés and other paid spaces for social interaction. This reflects a broader shift where public space is no longer treated as essential urban infrastructure, but as secondary to commercial development.

Short-Term Improvements

- Reopen and improve access to existing public spaces by reducing entry barriers and strengthening maintenance.
- Temporarily pedestrianise selected streets during weekends to create shared public spaces.
- Use underutilised public land and school grounds after hours as community spaces.

Medium-Term Improvements

- Make open space allocation mandatory in new developments, ensuring a portion remains publicly accessible.
- Upgrade neighbourhood parks with basic infrastructure such as seating, lighting, and safety features.
- Develop smaller, distributed green spaces across localities to improve access.

Long-Term Structural Changes

- Establish planning norms that prioritise public and green spaces over high-density commercial expansion.
- Create a connected network of parks, walking routes, and natural areas across the city.
- Legally protect key open spaces as urban commons to prevent future conversion.

Key Stakeholders

Urban Affairs Department, Shillong Municipal Board, Town Planning Authorities, *Dorbar Shnongs*, Private Developers, Citizens

Weak Environmental Governance and Pressure on Urban Commons

Issue

Shillong's environmental stress reflects both governance gaps and everyday practices. While laws and regulations exist, their enforcement remains inconsistent and often not visible, contributing to the degradation of key natural systems. This is evident in the condition of *Wah Umkhrah*, where pollution and waste have become part of the river's everyday reality, affecting not only the environment but also public health and quality of life. Even more so when we look at Marten Landfill, which is Shillong's only waste dumping ground.

At the same time, decisions around the use of natural assets raise concerns about long-term sustainability and access. The leasing of 66 acres of Lumpondeng Island in Umiam Lake to a private entity, for instance, brings into question how ecological spaces are governed and who they are ultimately meant to serve. Together, these reflect a broader tension between economic use and environmental protection.

Responsibility, however, is not one-sided. While institutional enforcement remains weak, everyday civic practices such as waste disposal and littering continue to place additional pressure on the city's environment. This dual gap between policy and practice allows environmental decline to persist.

Short-Term Improvements

- Strengthen enforcement of existing environmental regulations, particularly around waste disposal and water pollution.
- Increase visibility of action through regular monitoring, public reporting, and penalties for violations.
- Support and scale existing community-led clean-up efforts by providing logistical backing, coordination, and recognition to active citizen groups and NGOs.

Medium-Term Improvements

- Establish transparent guidelines for leasing and commercial use of natural resources.
- Improve coordination between departments handling environment, tourism, and urban development.
- Introduce stricter monitoring systems for waste disposal and pollution in critical areas such as Wah Umkhrah.

POLICY INSIGHTS

Long-Term Structural Changes

- Legally protect key ecological areas as urban commons with clear restrictions on commercial use.
- Integrate environmental safeguards into all urban planning and land-use decisions.
- Strengthen institutional accountability through independent monitoring and enforcement mechanisms.

Key Stakeholders

Meghalaya State Pollution Control Board, Urban Affairs Department, Shillong Municipal Board, Dorbar Shnongs, Community Groups, NGOs, Citizens

Fragmented Local Governance and Accountability Gaps

Issue

Shillong's governance is shaped by a mix of state institutions, the Shillong Municipal Board, the Cantonment Board, and *Dorbar Shnongs*, each playing a role in how the city functions. While this layered system reflects local realities, in practice, it often leads to blurred responsibilities, uneven coordination, and gaps in implementation. For residents, this shows up in everyday issues—unclear points of contact, delayed responses, and inconsistent service delivery.

Dorbar Shnongs continue to be central to community life and local decision-making, but their functioning varies across localities, especially in an urban context where challenges are more complex. While historically significant in managing community affairs, it is now often perceived as less accessible and less responsive to public concerns. Across institutions, there is a growing perception among residents that governance spaces are not always easy to engage with, and that responsiveness can be inconsistent.

Another recurring concern is the limited space for meaningful citizen participation. While awareness is growing, there are few structured and accessible channels through which residents can engage with planning, budgeting, or decision-making processes. As a result, participation often remains informal or reactive rather than sustained and institutionalised.

Conclusion

Perhaps ours is a city that is still learning how to change without losing what makes it feel like home.

Ka Sor Shillong, as it is often referred to, has always had a way of accommodating and welcoming people, whether they come to build a livelihood, pursue their studies, or carve out a space for themselves.

What emerges is not a desire for Shillong to become something else, but for it to remain what it is, while working better for those who live in it. It does not need to become another city to prove its worth. Its strength has always been in its scenic beauty, its character, and its sense of connection, qualities that once drew colonial administrators to these hills and shaped it into a retreat from the plains, and which continue to define how the city is experienced today.

Shillong remains an unfinished story, shaped as much by its people as by its systems. Its future depends not only on better governance, but on whether its people continue to care, to engage, and to hold on to what still makes the city feel like their own. It is the city I grew up in, and the one I cannot imagine being completely apart from. Many leave, sometimes out of choice and sometimes out of necessity, but the desire to return never quite fades. **There is something about Shillong that stays with you, in ways that are difficult to put into words.**

Fig. 13: Bos Smit in Iewduh, parked and waiting for passengers.

Fellowship was partly supported by :

Jason Nicholas langrai

Jason is from Shillong, Meghalaya, with a background in Public Administration and an interest in urban governance and regional development. As a concerned citizen stepping into the development space, he is driven by a commitment to community-led change and the preservation of indigenous cultures, with a focus on building inclusive and responsive city systems.

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Message from the Founders

Ten years ago, we set off on a journey across India's small towns. Over five months and fifty cities, we came through stories, crafts, silences, and dreams. We rediscovered that our smaller cities were not merely settlements; they were living archives of collective memory and identity—fossils of space and time inhabited by breath and imagination.

In Ratnagiri we were directed by many city experts to meet an auto mechanic. He was the go-to person for everyone in the city, including the city government, for engineering issues such as the city's water supply. He had seen the city evolve and remembered its various extensions, its water supply networks, and the various issues the city had faced in the last few decades. In Thanjavur, we sat with a veena-maker working 20-hour days in a modest shed, carving centuries of musical tradition into a single piece of jackfruit wood. We listened to bakers, poets, priests, and students. They told us not only what their cities were, but what they could become.

What struck us most was this: citizens carry the city's soul. The insights they hold—about its past, its present, and its future—are powerful, yet rarely represented in how cities are imagined or governed. This realization gave genesis to the Nāgrika Fellowship. It has been our attempt to honour the power of local voices—to create space for young people to observe, listen, document, and co-create city narratives from within. Each City Vision Document is not just a reflection of one fellow's journey; it's a collaborative act of remembering and imagining.

We hope this document stirs dialogue, ownership, and pride. And just like cities that shape their people, we hope this fellowship shapes a new kind of citizen—curious, rooted, and ready to lead.

We exist to ensure small-city voices, often unheard, have the knowledge and tools to influence the development and policies of their communities.

We focus on citizen-driven research. By engaging directly with small city communities, we present their authentic realities, untouched by outside narratives. This hands-on approach keeps small city voices at the heart of everything we do.

Citizen-Centred

It's always about the people. Small-city citizens are at the heart of everything we do.

Curious and Objective

Our approach stems from curiosity—focusing on the truth, making sure every voice in small cities is heard clearly and fairly.

Credible and Rooted

We are committed to producing knowledge and insight from the small cities that is dependable and high-quality.

Resourceful

We make the most of what we have, using our resources wisely to create valuable knowledge.

Small Cities, Big Love

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